

Genotypic Analysis of the Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance Genes in *Campylobacter* species *in silico*

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Abstract

Campylobacter species is responsible for 400-500 million diarrhea cases worldwide every year. Emergence of antibiotic resistance has further complicated the scenario. A wide range of virulence factors and resistance genes are present in *Campylobacter* species and it is hypothesized there are genotypic variations in the prevalence of these genes. The study was conducted to investigate the presence of virulence and antibiotic resistance genes as well as to investigate difference in prevalence rate based on genotype through *in silico* tools. Among 26 species studied, sixteen isolates (61.54%) had the *cdtB* gene that breaks the double helix bonds. The *cdtA* genes were detected in ten (38.46%) *C. jejuni* strains while fifty percent (n=13) isolates harbored the *cdtC* genes. Ten isolates that harboured all three adjacent *cdt* genes were most toxicogenic. The lipo-oligosaccharides associated genes, *cgtB* and *wlaN*, responsible for β -1,3 galactosyltransferase production, were found in 7.69% and 30.77% of the isolates, respectively. About 57.69% isolates expressed *waaC* genes. Invasion protein *ciaB*, outer membrane phospholipase A *pldA* and IV secretory protein *virB11* were found in 53.85%, 34.62% and 7.69% of the isolates, respectively. Six isolates (23.08%) expressed both *tetO* and *tetA* genes while one isolate expressed only *tetA* resistance gene. Seven isolates (26.92%) had changes in *gyrB* genes that conferred the fluoroquinolone resistance. *In silico* PFGE typing found that genotype 3 contained all the virulence genes except *cgtB* gene while genotype 3 and 4 contained mutated *gyrB* gene. Genotype 1 and 5 contained no virulence and antibiotic resistance genes. Our data helps to predict the possibility of the presence of virulence and antibiotic resistance genes and helps to select appropriate antibiotic that are more efficacious.

Keywords: Antibiotic resistance genes; *Campylobacter*; Genotype; PCR; PFGE; Virulence genes

Introduction

Gram-negative *Campylobacter* species is responsible for traveler's diarrhea and gastroenteritis in humans [1,2]. *Campylobacter* is responsible for 400-500 million diarrhea cases worldwide every year [3]. Guillain-Barré syndrome is caused by *C. jejuni* [4] but virulence mechanisms are not well understood. Several studies found that contaminated food, raw milk, water, vegetables, seafood, atmospheric modified packed meat transmitted the zoonotic pathogen *Campylobacter* to humans during consumption or handling process [1,2,5]. Several investigations found that main source of food-borne human campylobacteriosis is poultry and poultry products [6,7]. During slaughtering, the intestinal tract of healthy birds and raw meat are contaminated with thermophilic *Campylobacter* species. In slaughter house, faeces and processing facilities during the evisceration process contaminated swine carcasses that ultimately leads to contaminated food products [8-10].

The mechanism of *Campylobacter* gastroenteritis in humans is not well known that limits the prevention of campylobacteriosis. Virulence factors such as motility and adherence of bacteria to the intestinal mucosa, invasion of enterocyte and toxin production may contribute to the pathogenicity of campylobacteriosis infections [11,12]. The most common virulence factor in *Campylobacter* species, the Cytolethal Distending Toxin (CDT) causes cellular distension which eventually leads to cell death [13]. The CDT has 3 subunits namely CdtA, CdtB, CdtC. The CdtB is the active subunit whereas CdtA and CdtC makes up the B subunit responsible for binding to susceptible cells [14]. Active toxin component of *cdtB* gene disrupted the double helix bonds in the nucleus and blocked the cell cycle [15,16]. The *wlaN*, *cgtB* and *waaC* are LOS (lipo-oligosaccharides) associated genes while *wlaN* and *cgtB* are involved in β -1,3 galactosyltransferase production [17]. These two genes are associated with *waaC* gene (which encodes heptosyltransferase I)

and connected with the Guillain-Barre' and Miller-Fischer syndromes [18,19]. GBS and other neuropathic conditions are caused because of molecular mimicry of *Campylobacter* lipooligosaccharide (LOS) with the carbohydrate moiety of gangliosides. The *waaC* gene, which encodes heptosyltransferase I, is responsible for transferring the first 1-glycero-d-manno-heptose residue to the inner core of LOS [20]. The *wlaN* gene, which encodes a beta-1,3 galactosyltransferase, is responsible for biosynthesis GM1-like structure [18] whereas *cgtB* (which encodes another beta-1,3 galactosyltransferase) catalyzes the biosynthesis of the carbohydrate moieties analogous to GM2 [18,21].

Invasion protein (*ciaB*), outer membrane phospholipase A (*pldA*), and type IV secretory protein (*virB11*) genes associated with bacterial invasion on epithelial cells, were found by previous study [22] but their functions are not well known. Phospholipase A, *pldA* was found to be expressed in invasive strains [23].

Several studies found that multidrug-resistant *Campylobacter* has increased worldwide due to misuse of antibiotics [24,25]. For the treatment of systemic campylobacteriosis infections, other antibiotics such as gentamicin, tetracycline and ampicillin have been used [26,27].

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Received January 02, 2018; Accepted January 22, 2018; Published January 29, 2018

Citation: Nahar N, Rashid RB (2018) Genotypic Analysis of the Virulence and Antibiotic Resistance Genes in *Campylobacter* species *in silico*. J Bioanal Biomed 10: 13-23. doi:10.4172/1948-593X.1000199

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Fluoroquinolones, followed by tetracyclines, are the most commonly used antibiotics in the poultry industry [28] where *Campylobacter* is ubiquitous. It can be inferred that over use of tetracyclines and fluoroquinolones have contributed to their resistance. Mutations in *gyrA* and *gyrB* regions of DNA gyrase and been held accountable for resistance against fluoroquinolones such as ciprofloxacin [29]. Majority of fluoroquinolone resistance of *Campylobacter* is developed by amino acid substitution at Thr-86 to Ilu though alternative mutation at Asp-90 and double mutation at Thr-86 and Pro-104 were also reported [30].

Resistance to tetracycline might be due to efflux, enzymatic alternation of antibiotic or by ribosomal protection. The *tetA* gene encodes efflux protein associated with pumping out tetracyclines out of the cell [31]. The *tetO* causes resistance by ribosomal protection whereas *tetX* gene encodes enzymes responsible for target modification [31]. Scientists identified that *tetO* protein recognized and bound with an open A site of the bacterial ribosome and conformational changes occurred that released bound tetracycline molecules [32]. Previous findings found that *tetO* also inhibited tRNA accommodation into the ribosomal A site and inhibited protein elongation phase [33].

Pulsed Field Gel Electrophoresis (PFGE) is considered as the gold standard for genotyping [34] and *in silico* data matched to that obtained in conventional method [35]. Our data helps to predict virulence and antimicrobial resistance profile of twenty-six *Campylobacter* species through *in silico* tools and also analyzes how pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) typing distributed the virulence and resistance genes within the genotypes. The virulence and resistance profile of future isolates with known genotype can be predicted according to our data.

Materials and Methods

Strains used in the study

Strains used in the study are summarized in Table 1. All strains were of human/ animal origin.

Primers used in the study

Primers used for detection of virulence and antibiotic resistance genes are summarized in Tables 2 and 3 [36-43].

PCR amplification

In silico PCR amplification was done in the website <http://insilico.ehu.es/PCR/> [35,44].

PFGE digestion

An online software <http://insilico.ehu.es/digest/wasdesigned> for *in silico* pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) digestion [35,44]. Restriction enzyme *KpnI* recognized the restriction sequence G₁GTAC₃C of *Campylobacter* species. Dendrogram construction was done in the website.

Results and Discussion

Genetic diversity of isolates

A total of 26 isolates were subjected to *in silico* pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE) analysis with *KpnI* restriction digestion that recognized the sequence G₁GTAC₃C of *Campylobacter* species. Band fragments were separated in 1.2% agarose gel and lambda ladder compared the band size. *In silico* PFGE typing grouped 26 isolates into five genotypes using 80% as a cutoff value (Figure 1). Genotype 3 was most prevalent followed by genotype 4 and 2. Fifty percent (n=13) isolates were present in genotype 3 whereas genotype 4 contained

Serial number	Isolate
1	NC_022660 <i>Campylobacter coli</i> 15-537360
2	NC_022132 <i>Campylobacter coli</i> 76339
3	NC_022347 <i>Campylobacter coli</i> CVM N29710
4	NC_009802 <i>Campylobacter concisus</i> 13826
5	NC_009715 <i>Campylobacter curvus</i> 525.92
6	NC_008599 <i>Campylobacter fetus</i> subsp. <i>fetus</i> 82-40
7	NC_009714 <i>Campylobacter hominis</i> ATCC BAA-381
8	NC_021834 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> 32488
9	NC_022529 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> 4031
10	NC_003912 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> RM1221
11	NC_009707 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>doylei</i> 269.97
12	NC_022362 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 00-2425
13	NC_022352 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 00-2426
14	NC_022351 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 00-2538
15	NC_022353 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 00-2544
16	NC_008787 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 81-176
17	NC_009839 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> 81116
18	NC_017279 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> IA3902
19	NC_014802 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> ICDCJ07001
20	NC_017280 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> M1
21	NC_002163 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> NCTC 11168
22	NC_018521 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> NCTC 11168-BN148
23	NC_018709 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> PT14
24	NC_017281 <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> subsp. <i>jejuni</i> S3
25	NC_012039 <i>Campylobacter lari</i> RM2100
26	NC_022759 <i>Campylobacter</i> sp. 03-427

Table 1: Name of the isolate.

	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size (bp)	References
<i>cdtA</i>	CCT TGT GAT GCA AGC AAT C ACA CTC CAT TTG CTT TCT G	370	[36]
<i>cdtB</i>	CAGAAAGCA AAT GGA GTG TT AGC TAA AAG CGG TGG AGT AT	620	[12]
<i>cdtC</i>	TTGGCATTATAGAAAATA CAG TT CGATGAGTTAAAACAAAAGATA	182	[12]
<i>cgtB</i>	TTAAGAGCAAGATATGAAGGTG GCACATAGAGAACGCATACAA	562	[18]
<i>wlaN</i>	TGCTGGGTATACAAAAGTTGTG AATTTTGGATATGGGTGGGG	330	[37]
<i>waaC</i>	TAATGAAAATAGCAATTGTTTCGT GATACAAAATCACTTTTATCGA	971	[38]
<i>virB11</i>	GAACAGGAAGTGGAAAACTAGC TTCCGATTGGGCTATATG	708	[39]
<i>pldA</i>	AAG AGT GAG GCG AAA TTC CA GCA AGA TGG CAG GAT TAT CA	385	[40]
<i>ciaB</i>	TGC GAG ATT TTT CGA GAA TG TGC CCG CCT TAG AAC TTA CA	527	[40]
<i>iam</i>	GCGCAAATATTACACC TTCACGACTACTACTATGCGG	518	[41]

Table 2: Primers for the detection of virulence genes.

about 26.92% (n=7) of the isolates. Genotype 1 and 3 and harboured about 3.85% of the isolates (Figure 2).

Genotypic distribution of Cytolethal Distending Toxin associated *cdt* genes

Toxicogenic activity of *Campylobacter* species is determined by cytolethal distending toxin which is composed of the *cdt* gene cluster containing three adjacent genes (*cdtA*, *cdtB* and *cdtC*). It was found that

three *cdt* genes determined the functional activity of CDT toxin [15]. Previously researchers identified that *cdtA* and *cdtC* are responsible for binding to target whereas the *cdtB* encoded active subunit of the toxin [15,45]. Sixteen isolates (61.54%) had the *cdtB* gene with 620 bp PCR product (Figure 3). Only *Campylobacter jejuni* subsp. *doylei* 269.97 didn't harbour *cdtB* gene out of the isolates studied. The *cdtA* gene was detected in ten (38.46%) *C. jejuni* strains with 370 bp gene product (Figure 4) while fifty percent (n=13) isolates harboured the *cdtC* genes. These isolates gave a 182 bp amplicon (Figure 5). The present study found ten isolates that harboured all three adjacent *cdt* genes and these were considered as most toxigenic strains. Genotype 1 and 5 contained no *cdt* genes (Figure 6) and hence such isolates are unlikely to cause gastroenteritis. On the other hand, genotype 2, 3 and 4 contained all three *cdt* genes. All the isolates present in genotype 3 carried *cdtB* genes while about 61.54% and 76.92% isolates present in genotype 3 expressed *cdtA* and *cdtC* genes, respectively. About 28.58% in genotype 4 expressed *cdtB* and *cdtC* genes while 14.29% isolates harboured *cdtA* gene in genotype 4. Twenty-five percent isolates in genotype 2 carried all three *cdt* genes. It must be noted that *cdtB* alone can cause cytotoxicity [46]. Hence isolates with only *cdtB* gene can cause gastroenteritis irrespective of the *cdtA* and *cdtC* although potency of toxin might be compromised. Thus all isolates from genotype 3 will cause diarrhea.

Genotypic distribution of genes associated with Guillain-Barré syndrome

The genes *cgtB*, *wlaN* and *waaC* are associated with GBS and other neuropathic conditions through molecular mimicry of LOS with gangliosides. The *cgtB* gene was detected in only two isolates and

Gene	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon size (bp)	References
<i>tetO</i>	GGCGTTTTGTTTATGTGCG ATGGACAACCCGACAGAAAGC	559	[42]
<i>tetA</i>	GCTCACGTTGACGCAGGAAAG ATC GTC ATT GTC CGT TAC	486	[43]
<i>gyrA</i>	ACGCAAGAGATGTT GCTGCGATGCGTTATACTGA	270	[30]
<i>gyrB</i>	ATGGCAGCTAGAGGAAGAGA GTGATCCATCAACATCCGCA	382	[30]

Table 3: Primers for detection of antibiotic resistance genes.

Geno type	Gene prevalence (%)	Gene functions
1	None of the studied genes were present	Diarrhea associated genes <i>cdtA</i> =cytolethal distending toxin subunit A, <i>cdtB</i> =cytolethal distending toxin subunit B, <i>cdtC</i> =cytolethal distending toxin subunit C
2	<i>cdtA</i> =25 <i>cdtB</i> =25 <i>cdtC</i> =25 <i>ctgB</i> =25 <i>wlaN</i> =0 <i>waaC</i> =25 <i>pldA</i> =0 <i>virB11</i> =25 <i>ciaB</i> =25 <i>tetA</i> =25 <i>tetO</i> =25 <i>gyrA</i> =0 <i>gyrB</i> =25	Genes associated with Guillain-Barré syndrome <i>cgtB</i> = <i>Campylobacter</i> beta1,3-galactosyltransferase B responsible for GM2 mimicry, <i>wlaN</i> =β-1,3 galactosyltransferase responsible GM1 mimicry, <i>waaC</i> =heptosyltransferase I. Adherence and invasion genes: <i>pldA</i> =phospholipase A <i>virB11</i> =plasmid pVir invasion-associated marker <i>ciaB</i> = <i>Campylobacter</i> invasion antigen B
3	<i>cdtA</i> =61.54 <i>cdtB</i> =100 <i>cdtC</i> =76.92 <i>ctgB</i> =0 <i>wlaN</i> =61.54 <i>waaC</i> =100 <i>pldA</i> =61.54 <i>virB11</i> =7.69 <i>ciaB</i> =84.62 <i>tetA</i> =30.77 <i>tetO</i> =23.08 <i>gyrA</i> =0 <i>gyrB</i> =23.08	Genes associated with tetracycline resistance <i>tetA</i> =Tetracycline resistance protein A <i>tetO</i> =Tetracycline resistance protein O Genes associated with fluoroquinolone resistance <i>gyrA</i> = <i>gyrA</i> subunit of DNA gyrase <i>gyrB</i> = <i>gyrB</i> subunit of DNA gyrase
4	<i>cdtA</i> =14.29 <i>cdtB</i> =28.58 <i>cdtC</i> =28.58 <i>ctgB</i> =14.29 <i>wlaN</i> =0 <i>waaC</i> =14.29 <i>pldA</i> =14.27 <i>virB11</i> =0 <i>ciaB</i> =28.58 <i>tetA</i> =28.57 <i>tetO</i> =28.57 <i>gyrA</i> =0 <i>gyrB</i> =42.86	
5	None of the studied genes were present	

Table 4: Summary of the results.

Figure 1: Phylogenetic diversity of *Campylobacter* species identified by PFGE analysis.

produced 562 bp gene product (Figure 7) while 30.77% isolates had the *wlaN* genes with 330 bp gene product (Figure 8). About 57.69% isolates expressed *waaC* genes and gave 971 bp gene product (Figure 9). These three LOS associated genes were found in only *C. jejuni* strains. The *wlaN* and *cgtB* genes were not found in the same isolates. Similar results were also found in previous study [17]. Not all LOS associated genes were present in same genotype (Figure 10). Twenty-five percent

isolates in genotype 2 expressed *cgtB* and *waaC* genes. All the isolates in genotype 3 carried the *waaC* gene while about 61.54% isolates in genotype 3 expressed *wlaN* genes. About 14.29% isolates in genotype 4 carried both *cgtB* and *waaC* genes. Hence isolates from genotype 3 are more likely to exert their pathology through the mimicry of GM1 rather than GM2 whereas the reverse is true for isolates from genotype 2 and 4. All isolates from genotype 3 would exhibit heptosyltransferase

I activity and would transfer first l-glycero-d-manno-heptose residue to the inner core of LOS.

Genotypic distribution of adherence and invasion genes

Invasion-associated marker (*iam*), genetic marker of *Campylobacter* species, identified in diarrhea and symptom free patients, was reported

by previous study [47]. Previous study found that clinical samples in children didn't harbor *iam* gene but isolates from older patients had the *iam* genes [48]. The present study found no invasion associated marker, *iam* gene. In Brazil, diarrhoeagenic *C. coli* isolates were found in children that had the *iam* gene while low prevalence of *iam* genes were found in *C. jejuni* strains [49]. Invasion protein (*ciaB*),

Figure 8: Detection of *wlaN* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 330 bp amplicon.

Figure 9: Detection of *waaC* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 971 bp amplicon.

Figure 10: Genotypic distribution of *cgtB*, *wlaN* and *waaC* genes. Genes encoding virulence genes are as follows: *cgtB*: *Campylobacter* beta1; 3: Galactosyltransferase B Responsible for GM2 Mimicry; *wlaN*: β : 1, 3 Galactosyltransferase Responsible GM1 Mimicry; *waaC*: Heptosyltransferase I.

outer membrane phospholipase A (*pldA*), and IV secretory protein (*virB11*) genes associated with bacterial invasion on epithelial cells, were found by previous study [22] but their functions are not well known. Phospholipase A, *pldA* was found to be involved in expression of invasion [23]. A study found that cattle isolates didn't harbour phospholipase A, *pldA* gene while sheep samples were potentially more virulent since carrying more *iam* genes than that of cattle isolates [50]. About 34.62% isolates (n=9) had the *pldA* genes and produced

385 bp gene product (Figure 11) in *C. jejuni* strains. Previous study found that *pldA* gene was encountered in high number (88-100%) in broiler samples [51]. High percentage (91.7%) isolates from poultry feces contained *pldA* genes [52]. Several studies described that *ciaB* gene is associated with invasiveness and a play role in progression of the disease [22,53]. About 53.85% isolates (n=14) had the *ciaB* genes with 527 bp gene product (Figure 12). Previously 98.80% and 61% isolates were found to harbor *ciaB* and *pldA* genes, respectively

Figure 11: Detection of *pldA* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 385 bp amplicon.

Figure 12: Detection of *ciaB* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 527 bp amplicon.

Figure 13: Detection of *virB11* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 708 bp amplicon.

[54]. Broiler meat samples and human strains equally harboured the plasmid associated virulence marker *virB11* gene that could invade the human intestine [55]. Researchers found that very small subset of *C. jejuni* strains carried *virB11* genes [39]. The *virB11* gene was detected in two isolates (7.69%) with 708 bp gene product (Figure 13). Nature of the plasmid and geographical differences are responsible for low level of *virB11* gene [52]. Several studies also found very low number

of *virB11* genes in the tested isolates [51,56]. Genotype 3 contained all three genes described above (Figure 14). About 84.62% isolates in genotype 3 expressed *ciaB* genes while about 61.54% and 7.69% isolates in genotype 3 harboured *pldA* and *virB11* genes, respectively. About 14.29% isolates in genotype 4 carried *pldA* while about 28.58% isolates in genotype 4 carried *ciaB* genes. Twenty-five percent isolates in genotype 2 harboured *virB11* and *ciaB* genes. Hence it can be inferred

that invasion and adherence by isolates from genotype 2 are unlikely to be mediated by phospholipase A. The same can be stated invasion via virB11 invasion-associated marker for genotype 4.

Genotypic distribution of tetracycline resistance genes

Tetracycline resistance gene *tetO* was detected by using two primers named DMT1 and DMT2 as described previously [57]. Six isolates were found to harbor *tetO* resistance gene and gave 559 bp gene product (Figure 15). Hence the prevalence was 23.08%. Forty-six

kilodalton membrane-bound efflux protein *tetA* exported tetracycline antibiotic from the cell [58]. Seven isolates (26.92%) expressed *tetA* gene with an approximate amplicon length of 486 bp (Figure 16). Six isolates expressed both *tetO* and *tetA* genes while *Campylobacter jejuni* subsp. *jejuni* M1 expressed only *tetA* resistance genes. Our data suggests that tetracycline resistance is more likely to be mediated due to *tetA* rather than *tetO*. Our data agrees with a study also found that more Kenyan isolates harboured *tetA* resistance genes rather than *tetO* [43]. Twenty-five percent isolates in genotype 2 carried *tetO* and *tetA*

Figure 14: Genotypic distribution of *pldA*, *virB11* and *ciaB* genes. Genes encoding virulence genes are as follows: *pldA*: Phospholipase A; *virB11*: Plasmid; pVir: Invasion Associated Marker; *ciaB*: *Campylobacter* Invasion Antigen B.

Figure 15: Detection of *tetO* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 559 bp amplicon.

Figure 16: Detection of *tetA* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 486 bp amplicon.

Figure 17: Genotypic distribution of tetracycline and fluoroquinolone resistance genes. Genes encoding resistance genes are as follows: *tetA*: Tetracycline Resistance Protein A; *tetO*: Tetracycline Resistance Protein O; *gyrB*: *gyrB* Subunit of DNA Gyrase.

Figure 18: Detection of *gyrB* gene. Isolates harbouring the gene gives a 382 bp amplicon.

genes (Figure 17). About 23.08% isolates in genotype 3 expressed *tetO* while 30.77% isolates in genotype 3 expressed *tetA* genes. About 28.57% isolates in genotype 4 harboured *tetO* and *tetA* genes. Hence isolates from genotype 2 and genotype 4 are equally likely to be resistant to tetracycline due to efflux pump and ribosomal protection. However isolates from genotype 3 are more likely to be resistant due to efflux pump rather than ribosomal protection.

Genotypic distribution of fluoroquinolone resistance genes

The *gyrA* gene that conferred resistance to nalidixic acid or fluoroquinolone resistance was examined [30]. Present study found no *gyrA* gene positive isolates (not shown). Seven isolates (26.92%) had the *gyrB* genes that conferred the resistance of fluoroquinolone antibiotics and gave 382 bp gene products (Figure 18). Our study is a contrast to previous report which states that fewer isolates (4.17%) were found to have silent mutations in *gyrB* gene when compared to *gyrA* gene [30]. Genotype 4 contained the highest number of *gyrB* genes (42.86%) followed by genotype 2 (25%) and genotype 3 (23.08%) (Figure 17). Hence resistance to fluoroquinolone in *Campylobacter* is more likely due to mutations in the *gyrB* subunit of DNA gyrase rather than the *gyrA* subunit.

Conclusion

Our study used bioinformatics aided approach to genotype and detect virulence and antibiotic resistance genes. Pulsed Field Gel Electrophoresis (PFGE) is considered as the gold standard for genotyping

[34] and *in silico* data matched to that obtained in conventional method [35]. The summary of the results have been illustrated in Table 4. We concluded that there is variation in prevalence across the genotypes. Certain genotypes are more threatening than others. Our data isolates from genotype 1 and 5 are not pathogenic since it didn't harbor any of gastroenteritis toxin genes (*cdtA*, *cdtB*, *cdtC*), genes associated with Guillain-Barré syndrome (*wlaN*, *cgtB*, *waacC*) or genes associated with adherence and invasiveness (*iam*, *pldA*, *virB11*, *ciaB*). These genotypes did not have genes associated with fluoroquinolone and tetracycline resistance. The cytolethal distending toxin genes has a higher prevalence in genotype 3. Since *cdtB* alone can exert cytotoxicity, all isolates from genotype 3 are capable of causing gastroenteritis. Based on the difference in the prevalence of Guillain-Barré syndrome associated genes among the genotypes, isolates from genotype 3 are more likely to exert their pathology through the mimicry of GM1 rather than GM2 whereas the reverse is true for isolates from genotype 2 and 4. All isolates from genotype 3 would exhibit heptosyltransferase I activity and would modify the inner core of LOS. Our data also suggests that that invasion and adherence by isolates from genotype 2 are unlikely to be mediated by phospholipase A. The same can be stated invasion via *virB11* invasion-associated marker for genotype 4. The mechanism of drug resistance also varies across the genotype. Isolates from genotype 2 and genotype 4 are equally likely to be resistant to tetracycline due to efflux pump and ribosomal protection. However isolates from genotype 3 are more likely to be resistant due to efflux pump rather than ribosomal protection. As for resistance to fluoroquinolone resistance isolates

from genotype 4 are the most resistant. All resistant isolates carry a mutated gyrB subunit of DNA gyrase rather than a mutated gyrA subunit. *Campylobacter* shows resistance to the clinically important antibiotics and this rising trend is a concern for public health. Therefore, enhanced research efforts are needed to understand the transmission, persistence and prevention of antibiotic-resistant *Campylobacter*. *Campylobacter* species acquired antibiotic resistance gene by horizontal gene transfer from either *Streptomyces*, *Streptococcus*, or *Enterococcus* species [59]. Seventy-five to seventy-six percent sequence homology was found between *tetO* gene of *Campylobacter* and *tetM* of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. The virulence and resistance profile of future isolates with known genotype can be predicted according to our data. Additional studies are needed to understand how antibiotic resistant *Campylobacter* emerge under selective pressure. Application of advanced approaches, such as genomics and proteomics, is expected to provide new insights into the molecular mechanisms involved in the development of antibiotic resistance in *Campylobacter*. Good hygiene practice and food safety assurance programs should be implemented to reduce the contamination risk during handling and processing. Misuse of antibiotics in animal feed must be reduced to control antibiotic-resistant *Campylobacter*.

References

1. Fraqueza MJ, Ribeiro SA, Pereira SC, Fernandes MH, Fernandes MJ, et al. (2016) Genetic and antibiotic resistance profiles of thermophilic *Campylobacter* spp. isolated from quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) in a Portuguese slaughterhouse. *Food Control* 59: 337-344.
2. World Health Organization (WHO) (2013) The global view of campylobacteriosis: Report of an expert consultation. Utrecht, Netherlands.
3. Ruiz-Palacios GM (2007) The health burden of *Campylobacter* infection and the impact of antimicrobial resistance: Playing chicken. *Clin Infect Dis* 44: 701-703.
4. Dingle KE, Colles FM, Wareing DR, Ure R, Fox AJ, et al. (2001) Multilocus sequence typing system for *Campylobacter jejuni*. *J Clin Microbiol* 39: 14-23.
5. Zhong X, Wu Q, Zhang J, Shen S (2016) Prevalence, genetic diversity and antimicrobial susceptibility of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolated from retail food in China. *Food Control* 62: 10-15.
6. Hafez HM (2003) Bacterial contaminations and risks from poultry meat and eggs. *Arch Geflügelk* 67: 146-152.
7. EFSA (2015) The European Union summary report on trends and sources of zoonoses, zoonotic agents and food-borne outbreaks in 2012. *EFSA J* 12:3547.
8. Weijtens MJ, van der Plas J, Bijker PG, Urlings HA, Koster D, et al. (1997) The transmission of *Campylobacter* in piggeries: An epidemiological study. *J Appl Microbiol* 83: 693-698.
9. Gill CO, Badoni M, McGinnis JC (1999) Assessment of the adequacy of cleaning of equipment used for breaking beef carcasses. *Int J Food Microbiol* 46: 1-8.
10. Gill CO, McGinnis JC, Bryant J (2001) Contamination of beef chucks with *Escherichia coli* during carcass breaking. *J Food Prot* 64: 1824-1827.
11. Dasti JI, Tareen AM, Lugert R, Zautner AE, Gross U (2010) *Campylobacter jejuni*: A brief overview on pathogenicity-associated factors and disease-mediating mechanism. *Int J Med Microbiol* 300: 205-211.
12. Datta S, Niwa H, Itoh K (2003) Prevalence of 11 pathogenic genes of *Campylobacter jejuni* by PCR in strains isolated from humans, poultry meat and broiler and bovine faeces. *J Med Microbiol* 52: 345-348.
13. Johnson WM, Lior H (1988) A new heat-labile cytolethal distending toxin (CLDT) produced by *Campylobacter* spp. *Microb Pathog* 4: 115-126.
14. Lara-Tejero M, Galán JE (2001) CdtA, CdtB, and CdtC form a tripartite complex that is required for cytolethal distending toxin activity. *Inf Immun* 69: 4358-4365.
15. Jeon B, Itoh K, Ryu S (2005) Promoter analysis of cytolethal distending toxin genes (cdtA, B, and C) and effect of a luxS mutation on CDT production in *Campylobacter jejuni*. *Microbiol Immunol* 49: 599-603.
16. Smith JL, Bayles DO (2006) The contribution of cytolethal distending toxin to bacterial pathogenesis. *Crit Rev Microbiol* 32: 227-248.
17. Müller J, Schulze F, Müller W, Hänel I (2006) PCR detection of virulence-associated genes in *Campylobacter jejuni* strains with differential ability to invade Caco-2 cells and to colonize the chick gut. *Vet Microbiol* 113: 123-129.
18. Linton D, Gilbert M, Hitchen PG, Dell A, Morris HR, et al. (2000) Phase variation of a beta-1, 3 galactosyltransferase involved in generation of the ganglioside GM1-like lipo-oligosaccharide of *Campylobacter jejuni*. *Mol Microbiol* 37: 501-514.
19. Gilbert M, Brisson JR, Karwaski MF, Michniewicz J, Cunningham AM, et al. (2000) Biosynthesis of ganglioside mimics in *Campylobacter jejuni* OH4384. Identification of the glycosyltransferase genes, enzymatic synthesis of model compounds, and characterization of nanomole amounts by 600-mhz (1)h and (13)c NMR analysis. *J Biol Chem* 275: 3896-3906.
20. Klena JD, Gray SA, Konkel ME (1998) Cloning, sequencing, and characterization of the lipopolysaccharide biosynthetic enzyme heptosyltransferase I gene (waaC) from *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli*. *Gene* 222: 177-185.
21. Antoine T1, Priem B, Heyraud A, Greffe L, Gilbert M, et al. (2003) Large-scale in vivo synthesis of the carbohydrate moieties of gangliosides GM1 and GM2 by metabolically engineered *Escherichia coli*. *Chembiochem* 4: 406-412.
22. Konkel ME, Kim BJ, Rivera-Amill V, Garvis SG (1999) Bacterial secreted proteins are required for the internalization of *Campylobacter jejuni* into cultured mammalian cells. *Mol Microbiol* 32: 691-701.
23. Ziprin RL, Young CR, Byrd JA, Stanker LH, Hume ME, et al. (2001) Role of *Campylobacter jejuni* potential virulence genes in cecal colonization. *Avi Dis* 45: 549-557.
24. Abdollahpour N, Zendeabad B, Alipour A, Khayatzaheh J (2015) Wild-bird feces as a source of *Campylobacter jejuni* infection in children's playgrounds in Iran. *Food Control* 50: 378-381.
25. Chen X, Naren GW, Wu CM, Wang Y, Dai L, et al. (2010) Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolates in broilers from China. *Vet Microbiol* 144: 133-139.
26. Allos BM (2001) *Campylobacter jejuni* Infections: update on emerging issues and trends. *Clin Infect Dis* 32: 1201-1206.
27. Kashoma IPB, Kassem II, John J, Kessy B, Gebreyes W, et al. (2015) Prevalence and antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolated from dressed beef carcasses and raw milk in Tanzania. *Microb Drug Resist* 22: 40-52.
28. Gouvêa R, dos Santos FF, de Aquino MHC (2015) Fluoroquinolones in industrial poultry production, bacterial resistance and food residues: A review. *Rev Bras Ciênc Avic* 17: 1-10.
29. González I, Georgiou M, Alcaide F, Balas D, Liñares J, et al. (1998). Fluoroquinolone resistance mutations in the parC, parE, and gyrA genes of clinical isolates of viridans group streptococci. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 42: 2792-2798.
30. Piddock LJ, Ricci V, Pumbwe L, Everett MJ, Griggs DJ (2003) Fluoroquinolone resistance in *Campylobacter* species from man and animals: Detection of mutations in topoisomerase genes. *J Antimicrob Chemother* 51: 19-26.
31. Roberts MC (2011) Environmental macrolide-lincosamide-streptogramin and tetracycline resistant bacteria. *Front Microbiol* 2: 40.
32. Connell SR, Tracz DM, Nierhaus KH, Taylor DY (2003) Ribosomal protection proteins and their mechanism of tetracycline resistance. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 47: 3675-3681.
33. Chopra I (1985) Mode of action of the tetracyclines and the nature of bacterial resistance to them. *Handb Exp Pharmacol* pp: 317-392.
34. Peters TM (2009) Pulsed-field gel electrophoresis for molecular epidemiology of food pathogens. *Methods Mol Biol* 59-70.
35. Bikandi J, San Millán R, Rementeria A, Garaizar J (2004) *In silico* analysis of complete bacterial genomes: PCR, AFLP-PCR and endonuclease restriction. *Bioinformatics* 20: 798-799.
36. Hickey TE, McVeigh AL, Scott DA, Michielutti RE, Bixby A, et al. (2000) *Campylobacter jejuni* cytolethal distending toxin mediates release of interleukin-8 from intestinal epithelial cells. *Infect Immun* 68: 6535-6541.

37. Wassenaar TM, Wagenaar JA, Rigter A, Fearnley C, Newell DG, et al. (2002) Homonucleotide stretches in chromosomal DNA of *Campylobacter jejuni* display high frequency polymorphism as detected by direct PCR analysis. FEMS Microbiol Lett 212: 77-85.
38. Godschalk PC, van Belkum A, van den Braak N, van Netten D, Ang CW, et al. (2007) PCR-restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis of *Campylobacter jejuni* genes involved in lipooligosaccharide biosynthesis identifies putative molecular markers for Guillain-Barré syndrome. J Clin Microbiol 45: 2316-2320.
39. Bacon DJ, Alm RA, Burr DH, Hu L, Kopecko DJ, et al. (2000) Involvement of a plasmid in virulence of *Campylobacter jejuni* 81-176. Infect Immun 68: 4384-4390.
40. Zheng J, Meng J, Zhao S, Singh R, Song W (2006) Adherence to and invasion of human intestinal epithelial cells by *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* isolates from retail meat products. J Food Prot 69: 768-774.
41. Korsak D, Dzierzanowska-Fangrat K, Popowski J, Rozynek E (2004) Prevalence of potential virulence markers in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* isolates obtained from chicken carcasses (in Polish). Rocznik Panstw Zakl Hig 55: 307-312.
42. International Standards Organization (2006) ISO 10272-1:2006 Microbiology of food and animal feeding stuffs-horizontal method for detection and enumeration of *Campylobacter* spp. Part 1: detection method.
43. Nguyen TNM, Hotzel H, Njeru J, Mwituria J, El-Adawy H (2016) Antimicrobial resistance of *Campylobacter* isolates from small scale and backyard chicken in Kenya. Gut Pathog 8: 39.
44. San Millán RM, Martínez-Ballesteros I, Rementería A, Garaizar J, Bikandi J (2013) Online exercise for the design and simulation of PCR and PCR-RFLP experiments. BMC Res Notes 6: 513.
45. Abuoun M, Manning G, Cawthraw SA, Ridley A, Ahmed IH, et al. (2005) Cytolethal distending toxin (CDT)-negative *Campylobacter jejuni* strains and anti-CDT neutralizing antibodies are induced during human infection but not during colonization in chickens. Infect Immun 73: 3053-3062.
46. Lara-Tejero M, Galan JE (2000) A bacterial toxin that controls cell cycle progression as a deoxyribonuclease I-like protein. Science 290: 354-357.
47. Carvalho ACT, Ruiz-Palacios GM, Ramos-Cervantes P, Cervantes LE, Jiang X, et al. (2001) Molecular characterization of invasive and non-invasive *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* isolates. J Clin Microbiol 39: 1353-1359.
48. Al-Mahmeed A, Senok AC, Ismaeel AY, Bindayna KM, Tabbara KS, et al. (2006) Clinical relevance of virulence genes in *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates in Bahrain. J Med Microbiol 55: 839-843.
49. Andrzejewska M1, Klawe JJ, Szczepańska B, Spica D (2011) Occurrence of virulence genes among *Campylobacter jejuni* and *Campylobacter coli* isolates from domestic animals and children. Pol J Vet Sci 14: 207-211.
50. Khoshbakht R, Tabatabaei M, ShirzadAski H, Hosseinzadeh S (2014) Occurrence of virulence genes and strain diversity of thermophilic *Campylobacter* isolates from cattle and sheep faecal samples. Iranian J Vet Res 15: 138-144.
51. Datta S, Niwa H, Itoh K (2009) Age-dependent variation of virulence-associated genes retained in *Campylobacter jejuni* isolated from chickens in a poultry farm. J Vet Med Sci 71: 1247-1249.
52. Khoshbakht R, Tabatabaei M, Hosseinzadeh S, Shekarforoush SS, ShirzadAski H (2013) Distribution of nine virulence-associated genes in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli* isolated from broiler feces in Shiraz, Southern Iran. Foodborne Pathog Dis 10: 764-770.
53. Rivera-Amill V1, Kim BJ, Seshu J, Konkel ME (2001) Secretion of the virulence-associated *Campylobacter* invasion antigens from *Campylobacter jejuni* requires a stimulatory signal. J Infect Dis 183: 1607-1616.
54. Feodoroff B, Ellström P, Hyytiäinen H, Sarna S, Hänninen ML, et al. (2010) *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates in Finnish patients differ according to the origin of infection. Gut Pathog 2: 22.
55. González-Hein G, Huaracán B, García P, Figueroa G (2014) Prevalence of virulence genes in strains of *Campylobacter jejuni* isolated from human, bovine and broiler. Braz J Microbiol 44: 1223-1229.
56. Bang DD, Scheutz F, Ahrens P, Pedersen K, Blom J, et al. 2001. Prevalence of cytolethal distending toxin (cdt) genes and CDT production in *Campylobacter* spp. isolated from Danish broilers. J Med Microbiol 50: 1087-1094.
57. Mazi W, Senok AC, Al-Mahmeed A, Arzese A, Bindayna, K, et al. (2008) Trends in antibiotic sensitivity pattern and molecular detection of tet(O)-mediated tetracycline resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* isolates from human and poultry sources. Jpn J Infect Dis 61: 82-84.
58. Chopra I, Roberts M (2001) Tetracycline antibiotics: mode of action, applications, molecular biology, and epidemiology of bacterial resistance. Microbiol Mol Rev 62: 232-260.
59. Batchelor RA, Pearson BM, Friis LM, Guerry P, Wells JM (2004) Nucleotide sequences and comparison of two large conjugative plasmids from different *Campylobacter* species. Microbiology 150: 3507-3517.